

Intelligent process monitoring of RTM production in Aerospace

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1. ABSTRACT

Resin's resistivity has been proven at industrial level for sensing resin arrival, viscosity and online glass transition temperature for the whole range of composites manufacturing [1, 2, 3]. However, for dielectric cure monitoring, the existence of carbon fibres was always creating a challenging environment i.e. measuring the exceptionally low conductivity of the resin in the existence of highly conductive carbon fibres. So for conventional dielectric sensors, a glass fabric is necessary to isolate the sensing area from the carbon fibres but in 2019, a new type of dielectric durable cure sensor that doesn't need any protection from carbon fibres was launched and tested successfully [4] under real conditions in the production of CFRP flat panels.

In the Morpho project, a new resin arrival only sensor has been developed to cope with carbon fibres while it is the first time that all our innovations are implemented in a challenging RTM aerospace application. For the real-time provision of resin viscosity, an extensive study of the correlation between resistivity and viscosity evolution as well as the effect of storage aging to both the viscosity and resistivity have been studied with the aim to provide a viscosity estimation online during injection and holding together with the glass transition temperature estimation during curing. The system has been used in a series of injection trials at Safran Composites and the first results are particularly promising.

2. INTRODUCTION

In aerospace, the development of the liquid composite moulding processes has been relied mainly on trial and error because of the lack of non-intrusive monitoring means. Although the advancement of dielectric sensing has helped engineers to gain some insight of the closed moulding conditions, the existence of carbon fibres in contact with the sensors has significantly limited their adoption at industrial level.

In conventional dielectric (AC) cure monitoring, a range of sinusoidal electrical excitation is applied to the electrodes of a comp sensor which is in contact with the material under investigation so that the measured electric properties provide information about the material state. Although significant effort has been devoted in this technology for more than 30 years, only laboratory and very limited industrial scale applications exist. On the other hand, the DC-based dielectric cure monitoring system, namely the Optimold system, was presented in 2010 [5] with a clear focus on industrial applications. The Optimold system measures directly the resin's electrical resistance and temperature using specialised sensors and is capable for the in-situ monitoring of the full transformation of a thermoset resin i.e. from very low viscous resins at high temperatures to fully cured resins at room temperature with the resistance ranging from 10^5 Ohm up to 10^{14} Ohm. Comparison between the DC and AC cure monitoring systems has demonstrated the superiority of the DC technology in sensing the complete transformation of thermoset resins. Furthermore, the DC-based system is cheaper, very easy to use and very reliable and robust as it has been proven in various industrial installations in wind energy, automotive and aerospace production lines [1, 2, 3, 6]. Last but not least, in contrast to the AC dielectric systems, the DC-based sensing is significantly less vulnerable to carbon fibres due to its inherited superficial electric field so with a suitable sensor design it can be used in industrial CFRP production without any extra protection [4]. The developed cure sensor [4]

has an integrated temperature sensor measuring accurately the temperature close to the resin which is absolutely necessary in conjunction with the resistivity, for the online calculation of the resin's viscosity and glass transition temperature (Tg) which are the most important properties in composites processing.

3. INTELLIGENT PROCESS MONITORING IN RTM

Although it is evident that RTM in aerospace is used everyday without much information from the mould cavity, it is also obvious that any real-time information of the resin state from inside the cavity would help significantly the development, the process optimisation and the online quality control of the manufacturing process. For example, knowing how the resin flows inside the cavity would help improving the accuracy of simulation methods and understand the process deviations while using this information in real-time could lead to control actions that could reduce scrap. Furthermore, the use of cure sensors should give better insight of how the viscosity evolves during injection and packing while the online provision of the Glass Transition Temperature (Tg) could lead to shorter cure cycles.

In Morpho project, one of the objectives is to use as much information as possible from the cavity and from around the mould in order to ensure optimum process control for the RTM production of the CFRP FOD (Foreign Object Debris) panel.

In fig. 1, an overview of the information that is provided by each tool-integrated sensor is depicted: besides resin arrival timestamp at several locations, the cure sensors measure the electrical resistance of the resin providing real-time information about the resin age/mixing ratio, viscosity, gelation and Tg.

Figure 1. Overview of the monitoring units used in the development of the global intelligent process monitoring system.

The main components of this intelligent system are analysed below.

3.1 The inline resin arrival sensor

The inline resin arrival sensor (fig.2) is connected to the Optiflow system (resin arrival and temperature monitoring) and can provide the time-stamp when the resin goes through the sensor i.e. when the resin enters or exits the mould cavity. The inline can be easily integrated at the inlet/ outlet gates without any modification to the mould.

Figure 2. The inline resin arrival sensor for the inlet and outlet gates of the RTM tool.

3.2 The CF durable cure sensor

The CF durable cure sensor (fig.3) was developed [4] to be used in direct contact with carbon fibres without the need of any insulation. Its performance was tested extensively in the production of CFRP panels for an automotive application [2]. Although in the current application lower injection pressure is used, the considerably higher curing temperature, the longer processing cycles and the higher fibre volume content has created a more challenging environment for this sensor. Furthermore, a new housing specifically for the Morpho project with a reduced sensor length was developed and used in these trials.

Figure 3. The CF cure durable sensor.

3.3 The CF durable resin arrival sensor

Although the CF cure sensor provides a resin arrival signal, it was decided to develop a dedicated sensor which can work in direct contact with carbon fibres to get the resin arrival information. The sensor that was developed here (fig.4) has an improved manufacturability while providing the resin arrival information at the high Fibre Volume fractions that is being used in aerospace. At the same time, the sensor works with the Optiflow system, resulting in a particularly affordable solution especially when numerous such sensors are needed.

Figure 4. Close-up the new CF resin arrival sensor, flush-mounted in the RTM tool.

3.4 The Cure Simulator

The Cure Simulator concept has been developed within a previous EU funded project [6] to provide a non-intrusive solution for monitoring the curing in autoclaves. As can be seen in fig.5, the idea is to monitor the curing that happens on the Cure Simulator's resin cell which follows in real-time and accurately the temperature measured at the point of interest in the curing component in the autoclave. The same concept has been also used in monitoring the curing of epoxy adhesives in wind energy production. In both cases, the use of the Cure Simulator enables the use of the cure monitoring where it is quite challenging to introduce in-situ non-intrusive cure sensors. Although for RTM this is not really the case, the use of the Cure Simulator may provide an alternative solution that can give us more information about resin aging/ mixing ratio, viscosity and curing in a more secure environment, especially if users are not willing to modify their moulds. Thus, in this project we have the opportunity to study further the suitability of the Cure Simulator to provide valuable information comparing it to the in-situ sensors that have been installed in the mould cavity.

Figure 5. The Cure Simulator concept for RTM application

4. RESULTS

For the present application, the mono-component epoxy resin 2896 from 3M has been used for the demonstration of the intelligent monitoring system for the manufacturing of an FOD panel in a steel RTM mould that was developed and manufactured by Safran Composites specifically for the Morpho project.

4.1 ORS calibration for Online viscosity estimation

Initially, a series of trials were executed in the lab to investigate the correlation between the resin's resistivity and viscosity. As can be seen in fig.6, the evolution of the viscosity at 165°C correlates very well to the resistivity of a fresh resin batch. It is very interesting to compare this curve with the higher resistivity observed for an aged resin batch also shown in fig.6. That aged resin batch was not out of spec since it was kept for 5 hrs at 100°C which is the recommended time limit by the resin manufacturer. However, as can be seen in fig.6 its initial resistivity (and its viscosity) are much higher and rises much faster than the fresh batch, meaning that it is of particular interest to validate the resin age before injection especially if the resin batch is close to expiration.

Figure 6. Evolution of resistance vs. viscosity for a fresh and aged resin at 165°C

4.2 ORS calibration for Online Tg estimation

As a first step for the calibration toward the online provision of the Tg estimation, a series of curing trials were performed with a small steel mould at the lab, producing also the DMA coupons that were analysed afterwards at Safran. As can be seen in fig.7, following the calibration, the evolution of the Tg during curing is reproduced very accurately by the ORS (Online Resin State) system.

Figure 7. Comparison between Tg measured by DMA and estimated online by ORS vs curing time at 190°C.

Following the calibration procedure, the ORS can be used to provide the online estimation of the DMA-based Tg as can be seen in one of the trials performed in Synthesites' lab in fig.8.

Figure 8. Resistance (left axis) and temperature (right axis) history and the resulting estimated Tg (right axis) in one of the DMA coupons produced in the lab.

4.3 Implementation at Safran Composites

Following the lab-scale development and the calibration, the complete system was installed at Safran Composites as can be seen in fig.9.

Figure 9. Left: The interactive touch screen/ PC that has been installed in front of the press, Right: the monitoring units and Cure Simulator were placed at the back of the RTM mould/press.

Three cure and thirteen resin arrival durable CF sensors were installed flush mounted at the bottom tool as can be seen in fig. 10. Two more inline sensors were installed at the inlet and outlet gates, together with a pressure sensor and the Cure Simulator.

Figure 10. The bottom tool with all sixteen in-mould sensors installed.

Figure 11. The produced FOD panel

Up till now, five FOD panels have been produced (fig. 11). An indicative output of the data-acquisition software can be seen in fig.12 and 13. In fig.12 the resin arrival times during an injection are shown when the timeline bar colours change from green to yellow.

Figure 12: Resin arrival time-stamps during resin injection.

The narrow variation of the temperature which is being measured by the numerous cure and resin arrival sensors across the mould (fig.13) ensures the very good temperature homogeneity across the mould cavity. It is very encouraging that none of the 16 sensors presented any issue or interference from the carbon fibres during the whole duration of the production cycle. On the other hand, the resistance curves measured by the three cure sensors show some variation which is still under investigation.

Figure 13. Recorded temperature and resistance from the various sensors and estimated online Tg during the production of a FOD panel.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For the first time, a full system for the intelligent complete monitoring of the RTM process for carbon fibre components has been implemented successfully. Nineteen intelligent durable sensors have been used to monitor viscosity, resin arrival and curing during RTM production. The Morpho project is on-going and further studies will be executed to gain a complete insight of the process and how these sensors can be used to optimise production.

6. REFERENCES

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